

Correlation Analysis for the Prediction of QoS in V2V Networks

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ABSTRACT

Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communication is an essential component of the Intelligent Transportation System (ITS), which enables real-time traffic data sharing and collective awareness among vehicles and promotes a safer, more effective, and environmentally friendly road traffic environment. One of the main prerequisites for a robust and reliable V2V application minimizing crashes, easing traffic, and reducing traffic congestion is an error-free prediction of the underlying communication performance. In this paper, we delve into the predictive Quality of Service (pQoS) for V2V communication specifically for IEEE 802.11p networks. We establish the correlations between main Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) affecting the V2V communication quality as well as provide recommendations on how these correlations can be used to develop a robust Quality of Service (QoS) prediction algorithm for forecasting and optimizing the V2V performance.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Networks** → **Network performance modeling**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Machine learning approaches*.

KEYWORDS

V2V, AI, IEEE 802.11p, QoS, prediction, machine learning

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1 INTRODUCTION

Continuous developments in the field of transportation have been made possible by the deployment of connected vehicles and the promise of seamless communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and pedestrians. A crucial aspect of underlying innovative safety-based applications is the V2V communication, which enables real-time data sharing and collaboration among vehicles and promotes a safer, more effective, and environmentally friendly ITS [11]. V2V communication can be described as the transmission of data between vehicles and road infrastructure components such as lane markings, road signs, and traffic lights [5]. It has lately attracted a

lot of attention because of its enormous potential to enable intelligent transportation, numerous safety applications, and on-road infotainment services. However, the greatest benefits of safety-related applications can be realized only when a large portion of vehicles is equipped with the communication system [7]. As the number of connected vehicles grows, it is more crucial than ever to guarantee a reliable and accurate QoS for V2V communication. Although basic V2V data exchange is supported by the current implementation, there is a growing need to improve the predictive abilities of these systems to deal with the challenges imposed by highly dynamic traffic scenarios, changing network conditions, and rising communication demands. Furthermore, the V2V network has to ensure a timely exchange of accurate information between vehicles regardless of the underlying traffic density and network conditions.

As vehicular networks' dynamic nature and the heterogeneous structure of their underlying architecture has resulted in new requirements and more complex computations; the short-time prediction of the communication performance becomes an important research area in this context [20]. Proactive solutions that foresee and mitigate a potential communication disruption before it arises are the goal of the pQoS framework, which seeks to go beyond reactive measures. Researchers and engineers are actively investigating new strategies to foresee and optimize the quality and reliability of V2V communication in real-time by utilizing cutting-edge technologies like machine learning, artificial intelligence, and predictive analytics [23]. The exploitation of machine learning techniques could increase the reliability of safety-critical applications by adapting network parameters according to the predicted traffic condition. Machine Learning (ML) can address issues with highly dynamic vehicular networks by adopting data-centric methods and can eventually help in designing algorithms for pQoS [15].

In this paper, we delve into the pQoS for V2V communication specifically for IEEE 802.11p networks. We explore the current state of the WiFi-based V2V communication technology and highlight the details of existing approaches. Furthermore, we discuss the importance of pQoS in V2V networks and explain how machine learning algorithms and data-driven techniques can be utilized in forecasting and optimizing the quality of V2V communication. Thus, we aim to establish the correlations between different network KPIs affecting the QoS in V2V scenarios. Moreover, we propose an overview of selected machine learning concepts that can be used for the prediction of QoS and improve the performance of underlying applications.

The remaining paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes an overview of current work on the evaluation of IEEE 802.11p. Section 3 provides details about the prediction of quality of service by proposing an online training chain for the prediction of QoS. Section 4 provides some useful basics about how pQoS and ML can

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be integrated and studied in the IEEE 802.11p standard as well as their applications in the vehicular networking domain. Section 5 describes the performance evaluation of a V2V communication scenario performed using a profound simulation campaign. Finally, Section 6 closes the paper with a conclusion and future work.

2 RELATED WORKS

The IEEE 802.11p-based V2V communication is a well-established and mature vehicular communication technology that has been profoundly investigated through mathematical analysis, simulations, and various measurement campaigns. The work in [13] presents a novel analytical model for 802.11p that accounts for mobility, the effect of transceiver speed on system reliability, channel fading, and the presence of hidden terminals. Findings in [10] indicate that the current specifications may result in significant performance degradation in dense and high mobility scenarios. In these investigations, simulation-based validations of the performance of IEEE 802.11p are performed. The authors explored numerous performance and simulation factors while presenting comprehensive simulation findings that included several general IEEE 802.11p characteristics. More significantly, the research assesses the effects of different data rates and vehicle speeds on the performance of V2V applications.

Several articles have also assessed the IEEE 802.11p's performance using the standard's actual implementation. The authors investigated V2V scenarios in urban, highway, and rural environments. It has been demonstrated in [16] that Wi-Fi-based V2V communication can meet the delay and throughput requirements for the majority of vehicular applications. The investigation in [2] uses analytical models to compare the performance of 802.11p in terms of road traffic density, modulation and coding scheme (MCS), and message transmission frequency, taking into account the capture effect and hidden terminal problem. According to this study, 802.11p is quite robust over short distances. Based on simulations, the authors in [14] compare the performance of IEEE 802.11p with other technologies for both the physical and MAC layers. After a description of the protocol behavior of the various communication systems, they found out that IEEE 802.11p provides greater configuration flexibility. The various communication technologies such as Cellular-V2X (C-V2X) and 5G New Radio V2X (5G NR V2X) performance were compared in terms of Packet Error Rate (PER) versus Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), range, and latency. The simulation results show that the IEEE 802.11p performs better in terms of PER and range at lower vehicle densities, but when the level of congestion increases, there is an increase in packet collisions. However, neither study paid much attention to dependability or mobility support as well as the potential of pQoS for V2V applications over IEEE 802.11p considering the mobility constraints; instead, it concentrated primarily on the latency and scalability difficulties.

While the timely exchange of information between vehicles over V2V networks is the main focus, from a larger network perspective, the idea of QoS prediction is not novel. However, there are very few published works on QoS prediction in IEEE 802.11p for Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) applications. The focus of earlier research on IEEE 802.11p QoS prediction has concentrated on forecasting throughput, and latency using network-based data as well as the existing work on delay prediction does not account for dynamic channel

conditions [21]. Research in [11] proposed a latency-prediction framework that focuses on QoS prediction for delay-sensitive V2X applications, which is possibly the most related work available in the literature, but the concentration is on mainly network-based prediction as well as the use of traditional Markov chain analysis. Nonetheless, we are interested in utilizing the benefits of machine learning to design a prediction algorithm capable of predicting key QoS metrics for vehicle-based data, for which it is critical to understand which KPIs will have the greatest influence on the QoS and will eventually be used as input features to the ML algorithm.

3 PREDICTING QUALITY OF SERVICE IN V2V SCENARIOS

Increasing data demand, varying road traffic densities, rapidly changing wireless propagation channels, and ever-changing network topology might challenge the provision of ultra-reliable communication for safety-critical applications in V2X systems [11]. Therefore, reliable and time-efficient information exchange between vehicles is an indispensable issue in the development of safety-related traffic applications. The vehicles must have the ability to transmit and receive urgent messages with very low latency, regardless of the underlying traffic density. The transmission requirements for various V2X applications differ in terms of latency, reliability, and data rate. Safety-related applications with strict latency and reliability requirements present the most challenging scenario [1]. Two factors in this situation are of particular interest to the automotive industry. The network can first predict in advance what QoS level it will be able to provide. Second, the network can alert a vehicle in advance so that the vehicle can take appropriate actions once it learns that the agreed-upon QoS cannot be maintained [21]. This is where the concept of pQoS comes into play.

Predictive quality of service is defined as a mechanism to provide autonomous systems with advance notifications about upcoming QoS changes [1]. It can be characterized as proactive behavior that allows for more effective network adaptations and gives applications more time to respond. For instance, the network may preemptively schedule human takeover if the upcoming QoS is insufficient to support tele-operated driving. This will help to avoid dangerous traffic situations. In terms of application effectiveness, cooperative self-driving systems must meet stringent QoS requirements for data rate, reliability, and end-to-end (E2E) delay, despite the highly dynamic nature of vehicular networks, where instantaneous KPIs fluctuate rapidly. The decay of such indicators results in poor communication performance, limiting the use of safety-related applications.

As a result, we believe that pQoS will undoubtedly benefit the ITS by giving applications more time to react and prepare for varying network conditions in a very short time horizon [6]. PQoS will aid in predicting future network changes by providing advance notifications about future or incoming QoS changes, thus assisting underlying safety-related applications in congested situations. This predicted QoS can be used in two different situations: (i) a centralized network is in charge of anticipating upcoming changes in the QoS, and (ii) a vehicle-based QoS prediction where the prediction

Figure 1: Vehicle-based online training architecture of QoS prediction

occurs in a decentralized manner and each vehicle is autonomously able to anticipate and adapt to future QoS changes [21].

As we are focusing on the vehicle-based QoS prediction, Figure 1 illustrates a potential online prediction chain for the provisioning of pQoS. The main module QoS Prediction Model, also known as the system's "brain" takes relevant information as input to assist the machine learning task. This module might contain one or several cascaded machine learning algorithms enabling an accurate and robust prediction of the QoS. The application demand module is responsible for the provision and aggregation of application requirements, for instance, a derivation of aggregated message transmission/reception rates or average packet size concerning running applications (App. 1, App. 2, ..., App. N). The network information module filters passive network information such as received power strengths or channel load according to the targeted application demand. It is also responsible for the provisioning of active network information, including consecutive packet loss rate, average packet arrival rate, or one-way latency. To predict a very short or long-term horizon (sub-seconds to minutes), knowledge about the vehicle's route provided by the electronic horizon module would be very useful. The electronic horizon is in-vehicle software that provides map data and dynamic road condition information to create a simplified model of the route ahead of a vehicle, ranging from a few hundred meters to several kilometers. On-board vehicle sensors such as cameras, LIDAR, or Radar could sense the environment by providing a 360° view of the vehicle surroundings. Moreover, collective perception enables the possibility of gathering environmental information through the sharing of data about the state of detected objects in the vehicle surroundings over multiple hops [9]. The fused environmental information from local perception sensors and collective perception data could be used to derive the channel load and estimate the radio shadowing level according to the vehicle density and environmental topology. Expert knowledge is used to assist the prediction task by deriving a bound of measured or estimated information based on communication technology knowledge and the basics of physics. Moreover, wherever sufficient input data are not available, accurate estimates

can be provided using intelligent data processing from the expert knowledge module. We focus on this work in developing machine learning-based approaches for an online in-vehicle QoS prediction by first investigating the cross-correlation between communication parameters for high-density vehicular scenarios.

4 PQOS AND ML IN IEEE 802.11P-BASED V2V SCENARIOS

With the explosive growth of vehicular applications, IEEE 802.11p Wireless Access in the Vehicular Environment (WAVE) has become a crucial wireless protocol for a Vehicular Ad hoc Network (VANET). IEEE 802.11p is one of the primary vehicular communication technologies in Vehicular Ad-Hoc Networks (VANETs) since its technical standard was approved in 2010 [4]. It employs the 802.11e Enhanced Distributed Channel Access (EDCA) with QoS support as a channel access protocol based on Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA/CA), in the sense that high-priority traffic has a higher chance of accessing the channel. Even though EDCA can provide differentiated services, there is still a chance that stations choose the same backoff value, resulting in packet collisions. Moreover, unpredictable delays may occur due to the random access characteristics of the mechanism. As a result, providing QoS for highly time-sensitive information enabling applications such as collision warning, intersection warning, and real-time voice or video would be challenging [3].

The current 802.11p vehicular networks have trouble operating as a result of their growing complexity because of uncoordinated deployment, distributed management, network densification, and continuously changing topologies, which can eventually make it hard to ascertain whether the network can deliver the resources and, consequently, the required QoS for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) applications [24]. As a result of continuous data exchange between vehicles through CAMs to keep updating the network about their statistics, a tremendous amount of data is generated by the connected vehicles, which is more dimensional and has more features for each of the considered KPIs affecting the QoS.

Thus, manual analysis of this large amount of data is laborious and time-consuming. The traditional reactive methods cannot capture upcoming QoS changes in vehicular networks. Therefore, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning mechanisms can provide a data-driven approach to solving these challenging network issues [15].

Machine learning currently identified as a crucial enabler for vehicular communication, can be exploited to study these KPIs affecting QoS and eventually can help to detect potential QoS deterioration by accurately predicting such changes and proactively notifying the application so that it can quickly adapt. By providing a sizable amount of data, ML techniques can aid in the development of a model whose output will be heavily dependent on the training data set for predicting the QoS [23].

There has been a lot of research in the context of applying ML to vehicular networks communicating with IEEE 802.11p wireless access technology [21]. Channel estimation, traffic flow prediction, location prediction-based scheduling and routing, network congestion control, load balancing and handovers, and resource management are some of the performance-improving areas where they highlight the use of ML in vehicular networks which are focused on network-based predictions [15]. There has been minimal work focusing on vehicle-based QoS prediction. Therefore, to construct QoS prediction models that can be used by the vehicles to estimate the changes in the upcoming QoS, a machine-learning approach will be very appropriate. However, the characteristics of the data set can have a significant impact on how well the ML model performs for untried input data for QoS prediction. Thus, the data collection technique as well as the choice of suitable ML algorithms are crucial for achieving an accurate prediction of the QoS for untried examples [8]. As a result, it is critical to identify which data should be used when developing the prediction algorithm. It is important to understand how the various KPIs affect QoS and what kind of relationship exists between them for V2V networks that use IEEE 802.11p communication technology. This is where our work comes in handy, as it aids in identifying and assessing the correlation between various KPIs, which can then be used as an input feature to an QoS prediction algorithm.

There are a plethora of machine learning techniques that can be used to predict future communication performance in V2V communication systems. Some commonly used machine learning techniques in this domain are as follows:

Regression Models: Based on various input parameters, regression models can be trained to predict the QoS metrics such as signal strength, latency, or packet loss [23]. These models can learn the relationships between various environmental factors like vehicle distance, speed, number of vehicles in the network, and the corresponding QoS metrics.

Classification Models: These models can be used to forecast the availability or reliability of vehicular communication links. These models can learn to classify different scenarios as good or bad communication conditions by being trained on historical data [16]. The output of the model can be used to make proactive decisions, such as choosing alternate routes or adjusting transmission power to ensure consistent communication.

Time Series Analysis: To model the temporal dependencies in V2V communication data, time series analysis techniques such as Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Averages (ARIMA) or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) can be used [17]. Future QoS values can be predicted thanks to these models' ability to identify trends and fluctuations in QoS metrics over time.

Reinforcement Learning (RL): By making wise decisions based on in-the-moment feedback, RL algorithms can be used to optimize the QoS in V2V communication. To maximize QoS, RL agents can learn to adapt their behavior and change parameters dynamically [20]. To improve performance and reliability in V2V communication, for instance, RL can be used to optimize resource allocation, such as power control, channel selection, and transmission scheduling.

Deep Learning: Neural networks and other deep learning techniques can be used to predict QoS in V2V communication. Deep neural networks can deduce intricate patterns and relationships from past data, which enables them to forecast future QoS metrics based on the state of the network today [23]. These forecasts can aid in resource management and proactive decision-making. A deep learning model, for example, can predict the expected latency with a 100 ms time prediction horizon.

Combining multiple machine-learning models using ensemble methods, such as random forests or gradient boosting, can increase the accuracy of predictions and lower the likelihood of errors.

In this study, our focus is on investigating the correlation between relevant KPIs for QoS specifically in the case of vehicular networking designs that use an infrastructure-less IEEE 802.11p network, which will give an understanding of how this interrelationship can help in developing QoS prediction models.

5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To investigate the correlation between communication KPIs and the underlying network load, we conducted a simulation study with realistic communication settings under different road traffic densities and presented the results in the next section.

5.1 Simulation Platform

Our simulation environment is a hybrid simulation platform composed of the well-known simulation tools Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO), which provides road traffic simulation, and OMNeT, which provides the basis for our network simulation, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Hybrid simulation platform

OMNeT is a discrete event network simulation library and framework that includes a plethora of infrastructure and simulation tools [22]. OMNeT has a generic component base that allows for the

assembly of compound components to form reusable components using hierarchical and simple components, and it supports various network types, routing protocols, hardware architectures, validation, and performance evaluation tools. SUMO [12] is a microscopic and continuous multi-modal road traffic simulation package. It enables the modeling of inter-modal traffic systems including road vehicles, public transport, and pedestrians. SUMO provides a bunch of tools that handle tasks such as traffic demand modeling, network design, and scenario visualization and can be enhanced with custom models. SUMO can handle large networks with multiple vehicle types with several car-following models. To support bidirectional communication with network simulators, SUMO includes Traffic Control Interface (TraCI) for several programming languages. To be able to simulate vehicular networks and thus provide a high level of realism, we extended Vehicles in Network Simulation (VEINS) which provides a complete vehicular communication model based on IEEE 802.11p, by adding dedicated radio propagation models, antenna patterns, and vehicular mobility models. With its coexisting technologies and components, VEINS enables highly realistic simulation of complex heterogeneous scenarios [19].

5.2 Simulation Scenario

The simulated scenario represents a bi-directional highway section with two lanes per direction. Although the total length of the section is 6 km, only a segment of 3 km length located at the scenario's center is used for statistical evaluation to eliminate boundary effects, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Simulated highway scenario

To analyze the impact of vehicle density, the number of vehicles in the network is varied from 20 to 500 with an increment of double every time, which is a valid number of cars in a highway scenario. Table 1 summarizes the simulation parameters that all results presented in this section have in common. All these parameters were fixed during each simulation run, as we only consider single-hop broadcast transmissions in this study, and no congestion control was applied. We used the well-validated highway radio propagation model described in [18] which is based on a dual-slope path-loss model as well as a Nakagami model incorporating the effects of signal fading.

5.3 Evaluation Metrics

There are numerous applicable KPIs to assess the efficacy of V2V communication within highway scenarios. However, in this context, we concentrate on the following relevant metrics. As far as we know, these metrics are poised to provide optimal insights in scenarios characterized by high density and significant variability, both of which have a significant impact on overall communication performance.

Table 1: Simulation parameters

Vehicular Technology	IEEE 802.11p
Frequency	5.89 GHz
Transmission power	23 dBm
Message generation rate	10 msg/sec
Message payload	1000 Bytes
Data rate	6 Mbps
Channel propagation model	Highway Propagation Model
Antenna type	Omnidirectional
Highway length	6100 m
Number of vehicles	20, 40, 80, 160, 320, 500
Simulation duration	310 s

- One-way-delay defined as the time elapsed between the transmission of a packet and its successful reception
- Number of neighboring vehicles is the parameter that shows the number of neighboring vehicles that are successfully able to receive the transmitted packets from a given transmitter
- Packet loss rate is calculated for all vehicles as the number of lost packets over the total number of sent packets
- Consecutive packet loss is defined as the occurrence when several packets fail to sequentially arrive at their destination

5.4 Evaluation Results

As environmental parameters such as traffic density or traffic flow would be difficult to gather by running vehicles, we rely on successfully received packets to derive the number of neighboring vehicles and thus the current traffic density.

Figure 4: Number of neighboring vehicles with respect to loaded vehicles in the highway scenario

Figure 4 depicts the relationship between the total number of running vehicles and the total number of neighboring vehicles. As the total number of vehicles rises, so does the median value for the

number of nearby vehicles. The distribution's shape suggests that the median value is surrounded by a large concentration of nearby vehicles. This enables us to understand where the high probabilities of several neighboring vehicles lie, which in turn allows us to approximate the vehicle density in a V2V communication scenario, and eventually, that number can be used to predict QoS metrics such as delay based on the measured vehicle density. Additionally, we observe that up to 80 cars, there is an almost linear increase in the total number of neighboring vehicles, but the rate of growth for neighboring vehicles that can successfully receive packets after that is quite slow. One reason could be the high amount of interference caused by the increasing number of vehicles, which leads to more packet collisions, reducing the number of neighboring vehicles with successful reception.

Figure 5: Distribution of one-way delay under a varying number of vehicles

Figure 5 presents the Empirical Cumulative Distribution Function (ECDF) for one-way delay under varying amounts of vehicles in the scenario. We employ the ECDF plot because it can display the precise probabilities of successfully receiving packets within a specified one-way delay for various vehicle densities. The plot clearly shows that the average delay lies between 1 ms and 3.5 ms for all the vehicle densities, as well as a correlation between the one-way delay and traffic density. As vehicle density increases, so does the average delay for successfully received packets. Due to network congestion caused by the fact that all vehicles using IEEE 802.11p compete for channel resources using CSMA/CA and each vehicle has an equal chance of being granted access to the channel, the delay grows as the number of vehicles increases. As a result, the channel access time increases, resulting in a significant increase in one-way delays. For the total number of running vehicles between 20 and 40, all packets are successfully received with a maximum latency of 1.5 ms, demonstrating that IEEE 802.11p can efficiently handle lower traffic. After doubling the number of vehicles to 80, there is almost a two-fold increase in the average delay, but after

that, the scenario reaches a saturation stage, and there is not much change in the value of the one-way delay. One can conclude that the approximate expected one-way delay can be predicted, especially for low network loads, using the number of vehicles in a scenario as input.

The relationship between the number of vehicles and the Packet Loss Rate (PLR) is depicted in Figure 6 along with a 95% confidence interval. As expected, we observed that, in general, the PLR in the highway scenario could range from 25% to more than 70%, depending on the vehicular density. The results clearly illustrate the substantial correlation between the PLR and the network load as we observe a clear linear dependency between the two KPIs, which gives us an insight that this can also be used as an input feature while designing the pQoS algorithm. The prior knowledge of the network load in a V2V scenario can help the ML algorithm estimate the expected range of packet loss with a definite probability, which can eventually allow the vehicles to take appropriate actions.

Figure 6: Packet loss rate for varying network loads

Figure 7 depicts the association between vehicle density and average consecutive packet loss. It can be seen that the average consecutive packet loss increases as the number of running vehicles increases. We notice that when the number of vehicles is doubled from 40 to 80, there is almost a 50% increase in the average consecutive loss. However, as the vehicle density is increased further, the increment in the average consecutive packet loss decreases as the simulation scenario reaches a saturation stage and experiences extreme interference from the other vehicles in comparison to the sparse traffic condition resulting in a significant loss of information to the destination vehicle. Since these performance metrics are correlated, the average consecutive packet loss values can be predicted concerning future traffic density. Both the PLR and the consecutive packet loss can then be used to train the machine learning-based QoS prediction algorithm.

Figure 7: Average consecutive packet loss for varying network loads

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we discussed pQoS in detail and its significance for IEEE 802.11p-enabled V2V communication networks. A timely prediction of any degradation in service quality can greatly enhance the performance of vehicular communication. This work also gives an insight into the relevant communication parameters that might influence the pQoS most. We investigated the effect of varying vehicle density on V2V performance indicators such as delay, packet loss, and consecutive packet loss and analyzed the correlations between them. It is evident from the results that there is a correlation between the KPIs; which is mostly linear, and can be used as optimal parameters in designing the prediction algorithms for predicting the future QoS. We have demonstrated the significance of knowing the number of communicating vehicles in a network, which will be a key component in evaluating the vehicle's density when the QoS prediction is performed by the vehicle itself. There is also a brief description of the usage of ML for IEEE 802.11p-based V2V networks as well as about various ML techniques that will be very useful while designing pQoS algorithms.

In future work, we aim to design ML based QoS prediction models that would be able to predict any changes in the discussed KPIs; in such a way that rather than predicting a particular value of an intended KPI; we would also be able to predict a range for the KPI with a given confidence interval. We intend to broaden the scope of this implementation to include C-V2X and 5G NR V2X technologies to investigate whether analogous KPIs can contribute to better performance and improved prediction quality, or if additional KPIs are necessitated for this purpose. Furthermore, we planned to develop a machine learning-based application that will alert the vehicle about what to do in response to any QoS degradation. It is conceivable to develop an pQoS module based on pre-trained machine learning models as a service that can be integrated, customized to meet specific needs, and commercially distributed to registered users.

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